

RM ROADMAP

D5.4 Final Management and Coordination report

The purpose of this management and coordination report is to provide an overview of the activities, achievements, and challenges faced by the management and coordination team during the whole duration of the project.

WP5, Project Management, EARMA

August 2025

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Project full
title

**“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to
Strengthen the European Research Area”**

Project
acronym
RM
Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

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RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.4_D5.4 Final Management and Coordination report

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PU – Public (fully open, automatically posted online on the Project Result platforms);

SE – Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement);

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List of abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
CARDEA	Career Acknowledgment for Research Managers Delivering for the European Area
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ERION	Ethics and Research Integrity Officer Network
GA	General Assembly
M	Milestone
KCP	Knowledge and Community Platform
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RM	Research Management
RMs	Research Managers
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive summary

The purpose of this management and coordination report is to provide an overview of the activities, achievements, and challenges faced by the management and coordination team during the duration of the project. The report highlights key milestones, outlines the progress made towards organisational goals, and discusses any issues faced.

2. Introduction

This section provides a brief introduction to the report, including the reporting period, the team responsible for management and coordination, and the scope of activities covered.

Reporting period: 1st September of 2023 to 31st of August 2025

Team responsible for management and coordination:

- **The Coordinator (EARMA)** – is responsible for the financial, administrative, and operative coordination between the Work Packages, contingency planning and crisis management, as well as for the facilitation of internal communication within the project. They are also acting at the interface on all matters between the consortium and the European Commission. Specifically, the Coordinator is responsible for the day-to-day supervision and monitoring of project activities in line with the pre-defined timetable, ensuring fulfilment of all contractual requirements, coordination of activities between partners, organisation of project meetings, ensuring high quality of produced outputs, technical and financial reporting, including regular monitoring of project costs, follow up on EC payments, assistance to beneficiaries on specific administrative and financial issues, and carrying out periodic financial monitoring.

The EARMA coordination team includes:

- Nik Claesen, Managing Director
- Teodora Konach, Head of Professional Development
- Janina Bau, EU Projects Officer and Research Analyst
- Lorenzo Molina, EU Project Officer and Research Analyst

Scope of activities covered:

RM Roadmap charted a course for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support its delivery. It was conducted over 36 months and was funded to the amount of €1.5m by the European Commission Horizon Europe funding programme under Grant Agreement N. 101058475.

The overarching objective of RM Roadmap was to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

RM Roadmap allowed existing European networks to connect on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented consultation process in research management. This co-creation process gathered the existing

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communities and expanded upon them to reach two main objectives: to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners were working together on this project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HETFA Research Institute (Hungary); Nova University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (Belgium) and Una Europa (Belgium).

The work packages are as follows:

Table N.1 Work Package Overview

Work Package	Title	Lead Beneficiary
1	Intelligence	HETFA
2	Training and Development	NOVA
3	Roadmap and Advocacy	EARMA
4	Community, Communication and Dissemination	CHX
5	Project Management	EARMA
6	Sustainability and Exploitation	ASTP

3. Collaboration and Communication: Project goals and objectives

This section outlines the goals and objectives reached by the consortium during the project, including key performance indicators (KPIs) and other metrics used to measure progress.

Table N. 2 Collaboration and Communication: Goals, objectives and key performance indicators (KPIs)

Goal/Objective	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Project management platform operational.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RM Roadmap has an EMDESK licence of 15 users and unlimited guests. The owner of the platform is the coordinator, EARMA. All notes from general assemblies, executive meetings and all consensus documents from the co-creation sessions have been uploaded on EMDESK.
All deliverables and milestones achieved.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 21 deliverables and 9 milestones have been achieved during the period.
Advisory Board (AB) members pro-actively involved.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AB members were invited to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> All project General Assembly (GA) meetings (four physical on 8th of September 2022 and 8th of May 2023 one on the 13th of March 2024 in Lisbon, and the last one on the 19th-20th of March 2025 in Nicosia). 1st ambassador meeting in Budapest, back-to-back with European Research Area Action 17 workshop, 8th-9th of May 2023, Budapest, Hungary, second ambassador meeting on the 13th of March 2024, and the third ambassador meeting on the 12th and 13th of November 2024 online, as well as in the final in-person event on the 24th of June 2025 in Brussels. Furthermore, AB members have been invited to online events after the end of the project, including the dissemination online event in September 2025 and the last online ambassador Meeting in November 2025. Review project deliverables according to their expertise.
WP and Task leaders activated through dedicated regular meetings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 14 meetings have been organised on a regular basis. Agendas and meeting minutes were collected in the EMDESK common project management tool.

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<p>Collaboration with sister project from the same call (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01) CARDEA ongoing on a regular basis.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One physical meeting organised in November (25th of November 2022) in Leuven, Belgium between project coordinators: EARMA and University College Cork (UCC). ● 5 physical or online meetings organised (21st of September 2022, 24th of October 2022, 14th of February 2023, 11th of April 2023, 6th of June 2023) between coordinators EARMA, UCC as well as main WP leaders in common identified activities (HETFA, NOVA, University of Macerata, CERCA). ● Crowdhelix organised an online clustering event with the CARDEA project on 05.12.2024. ● Collaboration with CARDEA in WP2 to build an online platform showing professional development opportunities available in Europe. ● Collaboration with CARDEA to adjust and finalise the RM Comp has been carried out between April 2024 and November 2024. ● Invitation to join all 3 ambassador Meetings and the final event. ● CARDEA project has been promoted on the RM ROADMAP website. Both projects have linked each other's tools and websites.
<p>Project partners disseminated the project in dedicated external events.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The project partners effectively disseminated the project's scope and outcomes in about 95 distinct external events.
<p>Communication about the project through newsletters, articles etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The project's progress and achievements were communicated via 15 targeted outputs, including newsletters and articles.
<p>Ambassador Network established.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recruitment of (national) ambassadors has been completed by 31st of May 2023 (milestone 3). 115 ambassadors and associate ambassadors from 40 European countries have been recruited. This was complemented by the finalised recruitment of 35 thematic ambassadors in 10 different thematic communities by the end of January 2024. All of the RM Roadmap ambassadors had the opportunity to attend online trainings and 3 in-person ambassador meetings as well as 1 online ambassador meeting to prepare them for their mission and provide explanations on the

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	functionalities of the Knowledge and Community Platform. In addition to this, ambassadors received training material including step-by-step guides and FAQs as well as templates to support their task.
150 members enrolled under the Research Management Helix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Research Management Helix, hosted on the Crowdfelix open innovation platform, is an international community of RM practitioners, specialists, relevant policy makers and other stakeholder with 1093 individual experts from 369 organisations across 78 countries. The RM Helix has surpassed the KPI set for the milestone with 369 members enrolled under the community (August 2025).

4. Achievements

In this section, the report highlights the major achievements and milestones reached by the project. It includes a comprehensive overview of completed tasks, successful activities and other noteworthy accomplishments that contributed to the successful implementation of the project.

Table N.3 Deliverable Overview

Deliverable	Title	Month
D1.1	Preliminary report on ERA-wide landscape	12
D1.2	Report on ERA-wide landscape	34
D2.1	Preliminary report on professional development opportunities	12
D2.2	Online tool for professional development opportunities	24
D2.3	Report on the professional development opportunities	34
D3.1	Short policy brief 1	12
D3.2	Overarching Roadmap Plan	12
D3.3	Short Policy Brief 2	36
D3.4	Overarching Roadmap	36
D4.1	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan	6
D4.2	Online Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP)	6
D4.3	Activity report on KCP and DCE	12
D4.4	Preliminary Dissemination,	12

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	Communication and Exploitation report	
D4.5	Activity Report on the Knowledge and Community Platform	34
D4.6	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report	34
D5.1	Quality Management Plan	6
D5.2	Data Management Plan	6
D5.3	First Management and coordination report	12
D5.4	Final management and coordination report	36
D6.1	Sustainability Plan	12
D6.2	Final sustainability plan	34 (Deadline has been shifted to 36)

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Table N.4 Milestone Overview

Milestone	Title	Work Package	Month
1	Website	WP5	2
2	Knowledge and Community Platform Online	WP4	6
3	Recruitment of Ambassadors and Communities of Practice Moderators	WP1	9
4	Roadmap Plan	WP3	12
5	Catalogue of professional development opportunities	WP2, WP1	24
6	Data management plan reviewed and updated	WP5	24
7	ERA wide landscape	WP1	34
8	Online member confirmation data	WP4	36
9	Overarching Roadmap	WP3	36

Furthermore, major achievements for this reporting period have been:

- The establishment of the RM Roadmap ambassador network including 3 ambassador meetings with sessions open to the public, the first one attended by about 60 people, the second one more than 200 people, and the third one with 111 people.
- The final in-person meeting with 65 participants from 23 countries in Brussels in June 2025, including RM Roadmap ambassadors, RM Roadmap advisory board members, RM Roadmap partners, and representatives from the European Commission.
- 3 online co-creation session resulting in 102 consensus documents and 3 reports with more than 2000 people registered on the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP), discussing topics including the national landscape of research management, skills and competences, as well as training and a competency framework in Europe.
- Final report on ERA-Wide landscape of research management, including interviews and the RM Roadmap survey with 2212 valid responses.
- The RM Roadmap mapping exercise including a collection of 335 professional development opportunities for research managers in 39 countries, resulting in a one-stop catalogue for the research management community (available [here](#)) and feeding into the RM Dashboard developed in collaboration with the CARDEA project (available [here](#).)
- The dissemination of the RM Roadmap project by the consortium partners at about 95 events and by RM Roadmap ambassadors at 64 engagement activities. This included big events such as the EARMA

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Conference in 2024 in Odense and the INORMS Conference in 2025, which had specific session on RM Roadmap and a stand showcasing the results and offering an opportunity to engage with the wider RM community.

- The successful collaboration and clustering with other projects funded under Horizon Europe, including the sister project CARDEA, RM Framework and connections to EARMA thematic groups including the thematic group on Open Science, ERION and BESTPRAC.
- Two editions of the RM Roadmap "Train the Trainer" Pedagogical Training Course for Research Managers, comprising eight three-hour sessions and engaging 48 participants from Europe and beyond.
- Coordination of two RM TrainerLink online sessions highlighting best training practices and fostering connections and potential collaborations among RM trainers across Europe, with nearly 100 active participants.
- The organisation of two successful online workshops, which promoted project outcomes in a range of stakeholders (RMs, researchers, researcher network representatives, university network representatives, industry, policymakers, research funders). The first workshop was held on the 14th of February, 2025, and focused on the “The Added Value of Professional Research Management in the Research Ecosystem”. The event attracted 252 participants from different stakeholder groups. The second online workshop (12 June 2025) was titled “Research Management and its Roadmap Towards Professionalisation” and attracted 250 participants from different stakeholder groups. Both workshops included presentations of project outcomes, and were accompanied by an interactive session, whereby participants offered their insights on aspects of interest to the project, such as the RM value proposition and the roadmap developed through the project. The results of these interactive sessions were analysed and conclusions were used to inform the project going forward.
- Development of a best practice guide for establishing and maintaining RM networks. The manual, titled “A Practical Guide to Building and Sustaining Research Management Networks” was based on interviews with 19 representatives of RM networks across Europe, and aims to provide practical tips to support both emerging and established RM communities in creating lasting impact.

5. Success stories and challenges encountered

This section addresses the successes, challenges and obstacles encountered by the management and coordination team. It provides an analysis of the root causes of these challenges and their impact on the organisation's operations. Additionally, it outlines the steps taken to mitigate or resolve these challenges.

One of the biggest success achieved through the project was the establishment and recruitment of about 150 RM Roadmap ambassadors from 40 countries.

The commitment of ambassadors to the project, through their engagement with both national and thematic communities at the European level, has demonstrated the wide outreach of the ambassador network and its positive impact on national research management communities and networks. The ambassador network and the co-creation sessions, with more than 2200 participants have also shown existing gaps in terms of established RM associations/networks in Europe as well as available professional development opportunities for research managers.

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Furthermore, it has shown regional and national differences in relation to existing laws and policies related to RM in Europe. Additionally, the co-creation sessions have highlighted the need for a term and definition for RM that reflects the diverse roles and responsibilities and promotes the professional recognition of RMs and is adaptable to various national contexts.

Another success has been the participation of the broader RM community (over 2200 valid responses) in the RM Roadmap Survey, providing a snapshot of the background of research managers. The survey was completed by a broad range of experts at varying professional levels and has enabled the RM Roadmap project to provide a deeper understanding of who RMs are, where they work, and their education and experience. The survey also looked at the different areas of research management RMs are active in, as well as investigating Research Managers' preferences relating to a common terminology of the profession.

A comprehensive online mapping exercise was conducted and collected data on more than 350 professional development opportunities available to Research Managers (RMs) across Europe. This study aimed to identify existing training, mobility, networking, funding, and RM network opportunities, providing a structured overview of the landscape while highlighting key gaps and challenges in RM professionalisation.

The outstanding involvement of numerous stakeholders in surveys, co-creation sessions and mapping exercises is one of the projects major achievements.

The co-creation sessions resulted in 102 consensus documents and 3 reports with 190 pages, summarising the main outcomes with more than 2.000 people registered on the Knowledge and Community Platform. The outcomes of the co-creation sessions evolving around the topic of national networks and associations, skills and competences, as well as training and career development. All outcomes have been disseminated on the [website](#) and via social media to reach a wide range of stakeholders.

Launched in April 2023, the Research Management Helix has grown into an active virtual collaboration community with 1093 users and 369 organisations across 78 countries. A total of three Helix events were organised to promote the virtual community and the project and these events attracted over 200 participants and further connected the RM Roadmap project to other initiatives such as the CARDEA project.

Furthermore, the involvement of the RM Roadmap project alongside its sister project [CARDEA](#), in the development of the European Competence Framework for Research Managers (RM COMP)¹ that was published in January 2025 has been a key achievement.

In addition to this, the quality assurance and the involvement of the RM Roadmap Advisory Board in general assemblies as well as the review of deliverables resulting in outstandingly useful documents for the research management community was a success. Additionally, to ensure the sustainability and long-term impact of the project results, all deliverables will feed into the [RM Framework project](#). This initiative will leverage established stakeholder networks to support its objectives. The RM Framework project aims to develop a European qualification system for Research Management by standardising educational and training programmes and proposing a quality label to enhance interoperability and strengthen the RM profession within the European Research Area.

¹ More information available [here](#).

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Another success was the participation of ambassadors in ambassador meetings with more than 60 participating in the 1st RM Roadmap ambassador meeting in Budapest (May 2023), more than 200 participating in the 2nd ambassador meeting which was also open to externals (March 2024), and more than 110 ambassadors participating in the online ambassador meeting (November 2024). On top of this, the final physical event on the 24th of June in Brussels, was bringing together 65 participants from 23 countries, including RM Roadmap project partners, advisory board members, ambassadors, and other key stakeholders. The event served as a platform to showcase the outcomes of the RM Roadmap project. The meeting started with a session focusing on the engagement and contributions of ambassadors, highlighting their mission and achievements. The event continued with the discussion of the overarching roadmap, the project's final and central outcome. Furthermore, an interactive session engaged participants in discussion groups on key topics such as career framework for research managers, skills and competencies, career development and the recognition of research managers. These sessions fostered lively and productive exchanges among participants. The event concluded with a call to action, focusing on the future of the RM Roadmap and the sustainability of the ambassador network. In addition to this in-person event, an online dissemination event is scheduled for September 2025, followed by a final online meeting with ambassadors, advisory board members, and the RM Roadmap consortium in November 2025.

One of the challenges faced throughout the duration of the RM Roadmap project was the engagement of various groups of research managers, many of whom might have felt overwhelmed by the various surveys and co-creation exercises targeting them. This has led to lower participation rates. To address these challenges and ensure broader engagement, the consortium implemented a targeted communication strategy in a timely manner. This included identifying countries and thematic communities with lower response rates and tailoring communication efforts to the specific needs and characteristics of each targeted group. By using timely, focused messaging and leveraging existing networks, the project was able to reach a more diverse and representative group of research managers across Europe.

Another challenge was related to the co-creation sessions on the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP), as the initial timeline had been established before the first co-creation session took place. After the first co-creation session, the consortium evaluated the process, also based on the feedback received from RM Roadmap ambassadors and decided to adjust the timeline. This has allowed for a longer and more impactful co-creation sessions. To better support ambassadors in their efforts, the consortium provided training materials and templates to help them engage stakeholders more effectively. Additionally, managing and coordinating the RM Roadmap ambassador networks proved challenging due to varying levels of engagement and changes in participation. This was addressed by strengthening links with existing networks and engaging already established thematic groups within EARMA. This approach helped further engage the community, stabilise ambassador involvement and facilitated more effective outreach at both national and thematic levels.

Table 5 Success stories based on the identification of critical risks for implementation

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	WP(s) involved	Risk-mitigation measures
<p><i>ERA Action 17 activities and related workshops are taking place at the same time as RM Roadmap project activities.</i></p> <p>On the one hand, this empowers the overall momentum for a better recognition and understanding of the research management profession in Europe; on the other hand, regular communication flow is needed considering that activities at European and project level are developed at the same time. Some mitigation measures are presented in this table.</p> <p>Likelihood: High</p>	<p>WP1, WP3, WP5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RM Roadmap was represented by the project coordinator, Nik Claesen in ERA Action 17 workshops (e.g. 16th of March, 10th of May 2023, June 2025). RM Roadmap coordinator is invited as an official stakeholder in the ERA Action 17 meetings organised by the European Commission. • The 1st RM Roadmap ambassador meeting, 8 May 2023, Budapest (Hungary) was organised back-to-back with the 2nd ERA Action 17 workshop on the topic of upskilling. • Regular communication exchanges were organised between the RM Roadmap project coordinators and EC project and policy officers. • The RM Roadmap plan (D.3.2) is aligning with the main pillars identified in ERA Action 17 (recognition, upskilling, networking, and capacity building). This was used as a basis for the overarching Roadmap. • RM Roadmap was contributing to the European Competence Framework for Research Managers (RM Comp) and used this to formulate the questions for the 3rd co-creation session. • In order to get the record number of respondents to the survey, the consortium decided to merge the surveys envisioned in WP1 and WP2. In addition, the survey was only launched once it was possible to gather a good community base – in this way overlaps with the CARDEA survey were avoided. • The fact that the launch of the survey was postponed also included carrying out focus group discussions during the 1st ambassador Meeting, to gather empirical data for D1.1 Preliminary Report. This required additional efforts compared to the original plans, however,

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		<p>resulted in rich evidence for the preparation of the report.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lastly, compared to the original plans, two more online interviews were carried out, which resulted in a bigger diversity of case studies in good practices in RM.
<p><i>RM Roadmap and CARDEA are two Horizon Europe projects funded by the European Commission under the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 call. The two projects started in 2022 as two independent competitive calls with different timelines and project deliverables.</i></p> <p>This clearly constitutes a coordination challenge between the two consortia.</p> <p>CARDEA started in June 2022 while RM Roadmap kicked-off in September 2022. In addition, CARDEA has a duration of 4 years compared to a duration of 3 years in RM Roadmap.</p> <p>Likelihood: High</p>	<p>WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The two projects were collaborating on a regular basis (see Table 1) to maximise project impact and avoid undesirable duplication of efforts or results. • Both projects were collaborating in the development of the RM Dashboard. • CARDEA representatives were joining the ambassador meetings to share their outcomes from the project. • A memorandum of understanding was signed in October 2023. • Strong collaboration with CARDEA took place to adjust and finalise the RM Comp • A CARDEA representative is part of the RM Roadmap advisory board and a RM Roadmap representative is part of the CARDEA advisory board.

Furthermore, the coordinator is closely monitoring the critical risks for implementation as mentioned in the project proposal and grant agreement. An update is provided below in table 6.

Table 6 Critical risks for implementation identified in the GA

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	WP(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
<p>Not enough data and/or good geographical coverage collected about research managers</p> <p>Likelihood: Low</p>	<p>WP1</p>	<p>RM Roadmap partners have access to 35+ EU and nationally funded projects, the informal network of European Universities, LERU, The Guild to name but a few between them. The engagement of stakeholders from the beginning of the project and their consultation during all project phases ensured the collection of significant amounts of data and case studies.</p>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ambassador recruitment initiative can already be considered a success story, primarily due to two key factors. Firstly, the quantity of ambassadors onboarded exceeded our expectations (149 in total: 114 national ambassadors and 35 thematic ambassadors recruited by January 2024), underscoring the compelling nature of the project's mission and appeal to potential ambassadors. Secondly, the level of engagement exhibited by those recruited was truly impressive. RM Roadmap ambassadors were reaching out to a range of stakeholders to receive input into the co-creation sessions. • The number of consensus documents and the input the project has received can be considered as a success story. • The number of respondents to the RM Roadmap survey was also outstanding with 2212 responses.
<p>Lack of participation at RM Roadmap events/activities</p> <p>Likelihood: Low</p>	<p>WP2, WP4 and WP6</p>	<p>RM Roadmap was engaging with a wide range of stakeholders outside the project by also making use of the ambassador network.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By August 2025, the project partners effectively disseminated the project's scope and outcomes in 93 internal and external events. The consortium communicated the project's progress and achievements via 59 communication activities, including online articles, posts, and newsletters that promoted the project on partner websites and social media, as well as through promotional materials. • In addition, the consortium has created a RM Roadmap presentation Tracker to monitor the reach and influence of the ambassadors network where ambassadors can document dissemination activities in their respective networks (e.g., presentations in workshops, trainings, events etc.) about RM Roadmap. RM Roadmap ambassadors have also reported a total of 64 engagement activities, both online and in person, at various events.
<p>Lack of coordination among partners, WP and Task Leaders project</p> <p>Likelihood: Low</p>	<p>WP5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The coordinator organised regular virtual meetings and exchange via email with WP leads and the consortium as a whole to ensure an open and transparent communication and management process. • 9 general assemblies also open to the advisory board members and 14 executive meetings including work package and task leaders were organized by the coordinator. All notes from the meetings are collected on EMDESK. • To further improve the project management, EARMA had regular (weekly) internal meetings to discuss tasks related to RM Roadmap. All notes were kept internally in a dedicated folder.

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<p>Lack of engagement of RM Roadmap ambassadors across Europe</p> <p>Likelihood: Low to medium</p>	<p>WP3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 training sessions were delivered for national RM Roadmap ambassadors, while one training session was organised for thematic ambassadors. Regular drop-in clinics on the KCP and onboarding material in the common folder were also set up. All of these trainings were recorded and uploaded in a dedicated folder for ambassadors. Furthermore, videos showing how to use the features of the KCP were uploaded in the folder. Each country and thematic community had a contact partner from the RM Roadmap consortium. Travel stipends were provided to support attending face-to-face training. Opportunities were provided to present at project open events, as the RM Roadmap consortium was providing ambassadors with dissemination material, including a PowerPoint template and Email templates. • RM Roadmap ambassadors have received regular updates via email, including onboarding documents. See onboarding document for ambassadors in Annex 2. In addition, each country has a RM Roadmap responsible partner as a first point of contact to ease collaboration, questions, doubts etc by email or informal online or physical meetings. The list of responsible partners and their contact details are published on the RM Roadmap website. A FAQ was prepared by the RM Roadmap consortium, which is available on the website. In addition, the coordinator has set up an internal folder for ambassadors where information from meetings, events and project related templates is gathered. This facilitated a better involvement of the ambassadors with the RM Roadmap mission and its communication flow. • Three trainings were organised on the RM Roadmap Knowledge and Community Platform. To help monitor the reach and influence of the RM Roadmap Network, the consortium developed a presentation tracker for ambassadors. This tool allows them to track their outreach activities, such as presentations at workshops, trainings, and events related to RM Roadmap. • The project consortium established a reimbursement policy for the participation of the ambassadors in the RM Roadmap ambassador meetings. 60 ambassadors participated in the first ambassador meeting in May 2023. More than 200 people participated in March 2024, followed by a third ambassador meeting with 111 participants in November 2024. More information below in section 7 Resource management.
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6. Resource Management

This section focuses on the effective management of resources by the management and coordination team. It includes an overview of the resources allocated and assesses their utilisation and efficiency in supporting organisational objectives. The focus for this report is on the budget for the participation in the ambassador meetings as well as participation of advisory board members and associate partners in the meetings.

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- Budget for participation of ambassadors in the three planned ambassador meetings: The 1st ambassador meeting was held in Budapest in May 2023. The project consortium succeeded in involving a high number of national ambassadors in this meeting (60 out of 115). The partner in charge of local organisation was HETFFA, experienced in processing reimbursement forms and in organising large European workshops and conferences.

The approach for this first meeting was truly inclusive, creating a momentum for the involvement and engagement of the ambassadors in the overall project strategy. The 2nd ambassador meeting was in Lisbon in March 2024, evolving around discussions on the co-creation sessions and the preliminary results of the RM Roadmap survey. NOVA was responsible for the practical arrangements (meeting venue, all the logistics, social programme, dissemination to and engagement of local stakeholders, etc. etc.), while HETFFA managed the reimbursement of the ambassadors. The 3rd ambassador meeting took place online in November 2024, discussing the outcomes of the RM Roadmap project and the value proposition which was drafted at this time as part of the project.

- Budget for advisory board and associate partners: CYI was responsible for the reimbursement of the advisory board members participating in project related events and meetings while EARMA managed the reimbursement for associate partners. To strengthen the board's expertise, two additional advisory board members were appointed, bringing in specific knowledge on research infrastructures, gender, diversity, and inclusion (see Terms of Reference in Annex 1). One member was also replaced in 2024. To minimise costs, General Assembly meetings were made accessible online and were recorded. All recordings are compliant with GDPR and the project's Data Management Plan. Furthermore, meeting notes and PowerPoint presentations were shared via follow-up emails, as well as uploaded to the dedicated folders on EMDESK. Additionally, both the project kick-off meeting and ambassador meetings were accessible online for partners and Advisory Board members, ensuring broader participation and cost-efficiency.

7. Conclusion

The RM Roadmap project has successfully advanced the strategic coordination and professionalisation of research management across Europe. Through strong collaboration among consortium partners, extensive engagement of stakeholders, and the establishment of a vibrant Ambassador Network, the project has achieved its goals in fostering a sustainable, inclusive, and forward-looking research management community.

Key accomplishments include the development of the Knowledge and Community Platform, the completion of all deliverables and milestones, and the successful execution of co-creation sessions and surveys. These achievements exemplify the project's commitment to both innovation and inclusivity. With over 2,200 stakeholders engaged and 102 consensus documents compiled, the RM Roadmap demonstrates a deep, evidence-based approach to shaping the future of research management.

Despite challenges related to engagement and coordination within a diverse and evolving RM landscape, the project successfully adapted through flexible timelines, targeted outreach, and the setup of internal communication structures. Moreover, the project's collaboration with its sister project, CARDEA, and its contribution to the European Competence Framework for Research Managers (RM COMP) further highlights its policy influence and the strategic steps taken to ensure its sustainability.

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The final RM Roadmap serves not only as a strategic guide for the future of research management in Europe but also as a legacy framework to support long-term community building, capacity development, and policy alignment. With strong foundations laid and enduring networks established, the RM Roadmap project has positioned the European research management community for sustained impact and continuous growth.

ANNEX 1 RM Roadmap Advisory Board

RM Roadmap Advisory Board Terms of Reference

Version 01/08/2025

1. Purpose

1.1 The purpose of the RM Roadmap Advisory Board [AB] is to provide independent, effective, and evolving support to the RM Roadmap project over its life cycle.

2. AB Members – Nomination and Term

2.1 The initial AB membership will be established by invitation from the RM Roadmap Project Coordinator.

2.2 AB members will serve on a voluntary and non-compensated basis, and for the duration of the project through 2025.

2.3 New members may be nominated by the RM Roadmap Project Coordinator, and elected by a simple majority of the project General Assembly (GA).

3. The AB Activities

3.1 The AB will provide independent observations and assessment of the RM Roadmap project strategies and performance at milestones in the project life.

3.2 The AB will engage and provide guidance on specific project issues escalated for its visibility and potential action by the RM Roadmap Coordinator, project staff, Partners and WP Leads.

3.3 AB members will be invited to relevant project conferences, meetings, events where their expertise is relevant.

3.4 The AB will be invited to provide feedback on core project-related elements, including project deliverables, in one or several work packages based on their expertise, e.g. assessment of methodology, comments on quality, inconsistencies, identification of gaps etc.

3.4 Other forms of the AB support will be defined through continuing interaction between the AB, the RM Roadmap Project Coordinator, and project leadership.

4. TOR Evolution

4.1. This TOR may be amended in alignment with the purpose in 1.0 by approval of the AB at any meeting.

Advisory Board Members

Ana Marusic

- Tenured Full Professor, University of Split School of Medicine, since 2008.
- Chair, Department of Research in Biomedicine and Health, University of Split School of Medicine, since 2011.
- Head, Center for Evidence-based Medicine, University of Split School of Medicine.
- Co-editor in Chief of the *Journal of Global Health*.
- Chair of the Research Committee of the World Association of Medical Editors.
- Co-Chair of the Cochrane Scientific Committee.
- Founder of the Cochrane Croatia, takes responsibility for Research as its Research Coordinator.
- More than 200 peer-reviewed articles and was heavily involved with creating the policy of mandatory registration of clinical trials in public registries which helped change the legal regulation of clinical trials worldwide.
- Among other awards, Meritorious Award from the Council of Science Editors in 2016.
- Former president of the European Association of Science Editors (EASE), World Association of Medical Editors (WAME) and Council of Science Editors (CSE).

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP1, WP3, WP5: ERA-wide landscape, Overarching Roadmap, Data Management Plan

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Jan Andersen

- Chief Executive Advisor at the Technical University of Denmark since 2015, Team Coordinator for Research Support DTU.
- Expertise in research strategy and research planning in a European context.
- Advised the Rector of the Danish Technical University, Rectors and Deans of the University of Copenhagen and the former Royal Veterinary and Agricultural University on the balance between the research level, strategic policy level and the administrative level.
- Expertise in EU framework programs.
- Strong European and global network of colleagues and business partners.
- Chairman for EARMA 2010-2013.
- Founder of the COST Targeted Network and since 2013 Chair of BESTPRAC with more than 500 participants from 40 countries.
- Headed the establishment of the University of Copenhagen's research information system CURIS (PURE). CURIS became the corner-stone for the development of PURE, and has now become a part of Elsevier.

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP2, WP3, WP4: Community of trainers, Community Incubator, Association building, ambassadors, Overarching Roadmap, Community building

Karl Kerschbaum

- Vice Director, Regional Network Coordinator at Euresearch. Senior Legal Counsel and Research Manager at the Euresearch Regional Office Zürich.
- One of the Network Coordinators and Vice Director of the Association Euresearch.
- Legal Counsel and Research Manager EU GrantsAccess.

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP2, WP3, WP5: Professional development, Overarching Roadmap, Management

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Kathleen Larmett

- Executive Director at National Council of University Research Administrators (NCURA).
- Co-developer of NCURA's Executive Leadership Program and has worked with emerging leaders for over 20 years.
- Consults with non-profit organizations and presents workshops on topics including: Board Governance; Leadership; and How to Develop a Non-Profit.

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP1, WP3, WP6: ERA-wide landscape, Overarching Roadmap, Sustainability of the outcomes

Kurt Deketelaere

- Professor of law at the University of Leuven.
- The Secretary-General of the League of European Research Universities (LERU), an association of twenty-one leading research-intensive universities (Oxford, Cambridge, Leiden, Leuven, Heidelberg, etc), since 2009.
- Chief legal advisor (2004-2007) and the chief of staff (2007-2009) of the Flemish Minister for Public Works, Energy, Environment and Nature.
- Chair of the Board of Directors of the Flemish Energy Regulator (VREG).
- Chair of the Flemish Environmental Damages Commission.
- Board member of a number of profit (MRBB, AIF) and non-profit (I-Cleantech) organizations in Belgium.
- Extensive number of publications in the field of EU Environmental, Energy and Climate Change Law.

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP3: Policy, Overarching Roadmap

Thomas Estermann

- Director for Governance, Funding and Public Policy Development at the European University Association.
- Member of several European and national committees, expert groups, editorial boards, advisory groups and contributes on a regular basis to higher education management programmes and national higher education reform processes.
- Published on the topic of university funding, governance and management.

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP3, WP6: Policy, Overarching Roadmap, Sustainability

Lluís Rovira

Representative from the [CARDEA Horizon Europe project](#)

- Director of Evaluation in the Research and Evaluation Area at the Agency for Management of University and Research Grants (AGAUR)
- Director of CERCA (2011-2024) and Deputy Director at AGAUR (2003-2009)
- He has a PhD in Molecular Biology from the University of Barcelona

Role in RM Roadmap:

- Proposed involvement in WP1, WP2, WP3, WP6: ERA-wide landscape, Professional development, Overarching Roadmap, Sustainability

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Marta Agostinho

- She currently serves as the Executive Director of EU-LIFE, an alliance of European research institutes in the life sciences that aims at promoting excellence in research and acting as a voice for research institutes in the European policy landscape.
- She holds a PhD in Cell Biology (2007) and completed post-graduation in Science Communication (2009). With more than 15 years of experience in knowledge mediation across international settings, she has held positions such as Invited Lecturer in Genetic Engineering, Director of the Communication & Training Unit at Instituto de Medicina Molecular (IMM) in Lisbon, Portugal (2008-2012), PhD Programme Manager (2007, IMM), and Project Manager (2012-2014, NOVA Medical School (FCM/UNL), Lisbon, Portugal).

Role in RM Roadmap:

- She is proposed to be involved in three work packages (WP) of the RM Roadmap: WP1, WP2, and WP3 with a focus on framework conditions, infrastructure, and advocacy.

Andela Pepić

- Currently the Head of the Centre for Development and Research Support (formerly Entrepreneurship and Technology Transfer Centre) at the University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina.
- Previously worked as a project manager and researcher at the University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Political Sciences - Institute for Social Research. From 2008-2013, worked as coordinator for Bosnia and Herzegovina within the Regional Research Promotion Programme in the Western Balkans (RRPP) at the Human Rights Centre of the University of Sarajevo.
- She was Chair of COST Targeted Network 1302 BESTPRAC in the period 2018-2019 and currently BESTPRAC core group member
- She is currently Chair of the Gender Equality Advisory Board at the University of Banja Luka.
- She is also actively engaged in WBC-RRI.NET H2020 project focusing on embedding responsible research and innovation principles into the R&I landscape in Western Balkans.
- She holds a PhD in sociology (2022).

Role in the RM Roadmap:

- She serves as a gender, diversity, and equality expert on the advisory board and for the RM Roadmap project.

ANNEX 2 RM Roadmap Ambassador Network: Onboarding materials

RM Roadmap – The Ambassadors' Network*

RM Roadmap: Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area

An important tool for the realisation of RM Roadmap's goals is the **ambassadors' network**. RM Roadmap Ambassadors will be national or regional community builders and online moderators.

Ambassadors will be recruited for the following roles:

1. Gather intelligence and input from national and local Research Manager (RM) community, gaining their perspectives for the RM Roadmap project;
2. Advocate for the RM Roadmap project's prospective users and promote the project resources and services in their home country;
3. Function as online moderators to inform the co-creation of the future of research management in Europe.

The RM Roadmap Ambassadors' Network is crucial for the project's long-term impact.

The Ambassadors' Network will both contribute to the creation of the RM Roadmap digital Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) and play central roles in ensuring its function and vitality.

Benefits of being a RM Roadmap ambassador:

1. Be part of a **unique international network of peers**, created to contribute to a strong and vibrant European Research Manager and Administrator (RM) community.
2. Access to **state-of-the-art training for RMs**.
3. Be regularly **updated on the progress** of the RM Roadmap project.
4. Be **invited to, and reimbursed for two in-person ambassador meetings** during the RM Roadmap project period.
5. Receive **free training** in community building and facilitation.

Requirements for becoming a RM Roadmap ambassador:

1. Demonstrated experience as a research manager/administrator².
2. Experience from national network or association:
 - a. In countries where RMA associations exist, written endorsement from the relevant organisation.
 - b. In countries where no RMA association or network exists, experience from international RMA associations and/or networks is desirable.
3. Experience as a trainer/teacher/leader/community builder for RMA, or other relevant professional training, is desirable.

² Example of research manager/administrator as identified under the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 call: research policy advisers, research managers, financial support staff, data stewards, research infrastructure operators, knowledge transfer officers, business developers, knowledge brokers, innovation managers, etc. This is a not exhaustive list. The RM Roadmap project will work on a more specific definition.

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Conditions:

1. The position as ambassador is voluntary and not salaried (not requiring contract).
2. Ambassadors are recruited for the duration of the RM Roadmap project (until 31.08.2025).
3. Ambassadors will be reimbursed for participation in two in-person ambassador meetings during the RM Roadmap project period.
4. Non-disclosure agreements and signing of GDPR documents, only as required.

Ambassadors Roles:

Ambassadors are representatives of their country or thematic community. They collaborate in the framework of the Horizon Europe RM Roadmap project and are expected to:

1. **Spread the project mission**, contribute to requests for inputs and dissemination of outputs.
2. Play a crucial role in the **development and testing of the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP)**.
3. Use the KCP to – together with the wider RM Roadmap community – **cocreate online Communities of Practice** that will act as virtual central hubs for the varying RM profiles.
4. **Promote** the KCP.
5. **Create a two-way flow of information in and out of the project** – enabling feedback from the RM community as a whole, governments, researchers and important stakeholders' perspectives of the current situation of the RM profession allowing for country/regional specific factors to be considered.
6. Facilitate the **creation of networks/associations and communities** within their home countries, where such networks or communities does not already exist.
7. Take the opportunity to **present at project open events** as well as **participate as trainers** to share their knowledge and expertise.
8. Create **interest within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)** where such interest may be lacking.
9. Contribute to the **sustainability and impact** of the RM Roadmap outcome.

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What is the difference between National (Country Community) and Thematic (Community of Practice) ambassador(s)?

National (Country Community) RM Roadmap ambassadors inform their national/local communities about the RM Roadmap project based on information given by the RM Roadmap consortium partners. If the ambassador is representing a community supported by a national network or association, the ambassador is expected to periodically brief that network or association.

Thematic (Community of Practice) ambassador Thematic ambassadors represent a theme or category (a subdivision of the RM profession). A 'theme' is here defined as: "groups of related tasks relating to specific purposes within the support and management of research, performed by staff members that are not themselves active researchers". Themes will reflect subcategories of the research management (RM) profession. The pre-identified list is not intended to be comprehensive. For the purpose of the RM Roadmap co-creation sessions, the project consortium had to limit the choice to a maximum of 10 thematic groups.

Written procedure for replacement of ambassadors

Associate Ambassadors will become ambassadors in case the appointed ambassador steps down.

Each ambassador will have a dedicated Associate ambassador communicated with a confirmation email by the RM Roadmap consortium. If an ambassador steps down, they will inform the RM Roadmap relevant contact partner. The RM Roadmap consortium will confirm the replacement of the Associate ambassador to the role of ambassador.

Role of Associate Ambassadors:

The appointed ambassador is the national coordinator and collaborates with the Associate ambassadors for the organization of tasks, activities, workshops etc. at national level.

Only ambassadors are invited and reimbursed for the physical meetings. If an ambassador cannot participate to a physical meeting, they can appoint one Associate ambassador to participate in the meeting.

Associate ambassadors will have access to the recorded sessions from the ambassador meetings and other online trainings or meetings.

Associate ambassadors will collaborate closely with the ambassadors in the moderation of the discussions on the KCP. The RM Roadmap consortium will provide a dedicated online KCP training in September 2023.

Conflict of interest

By committing to the role of ambassador or Associate ambassador you confirm that you have no conflict of interest of any kind, including of commercial nature.

In case of doubt about a potential conflict of interest, please contact EARMA at projects@earma.org.

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Code of conduct

The ambassador or associate ambassador is not officially representing the RM Roadmap project or consortium and cannot make any commitments of any kind.

More information

More information about the RM Roadmap Ambassador Network is available at: <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/faqs>

*Version August 2025

Annex 3: RM Roadmap Ambassador Testimonials

RM Roadmap ambassador of Spain:

If there is a formal national network in your country, how has this helped you to spread awareness about the RM Roadmap project? If there is no formal network present, please describe your community-building activities.

There is no formal network or association which supports 'Research Management' as such for the whole country in Spain, whereas there are several networks and working groups related to research management across the country which have been created as forums to share experiences and insights. They are either regional or sectorial, as such, they are focused on Universities, Research Performing Organizations or supporting Knowledge Transfer.

As RM Roadmap ambassadors, we sent direct announcements on the opportunity to contribute to the project to the networks and working groups in which we are involved or that we acknowledged. We asked them to provide their position as individual networks on the topics discussed to have a more consistent representation and to encourage the participation of their members in the KCP platform.

Indeed, the RM Roadmap project has been key to raising awareness among the different networks on the relevance of the momentum for RM recognition. It raised the need for the different networks to join forces and discuss common challenges, and, for the first time, work on a joint position to approach the Spanish Ministry on this issue.

Through your experience of RM Roadmap co-creation session 1, what challenges do national RM communities encounter in contributing to national and European R&I systems? Please state whether the presence or absence of a formal national network is a factor in these challenges.

The participants encountered several challenges which are still not well addressed due to a lack of a formal National network, such as the need to devote resources to ensure common objectives, an adequate budget for organising regular RM support activities, periodic meetings between the networks and working groups, tailored training offers covering RM needs, and proper communication tools/channels, both internal to each forum and towards external audiences.

In line with this, contributors denounced there is little communication between the different networks/groups and the difficulty for the RMs community to have their voice heard to actively contribute to the creation of regulations that would support the sector. They expressed the need to have a voice at a national level so that key findings that emerge from these European RM initiatives can have an impact on their career advancement, considering the specificities of the country's legislation.

This first co-creation exercise emphasised the lack of recognition of the RM role from both governmental bodies and institutions in the country, underlined the missing definition of the job, as well as drawing attention to the need for dedicated strategies and resources to secure RM career development and stability. Overall, it raised a consensus on the importance of addressing these issues to enhance the effectiveness and clarity of research management within the Spanish context.

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From your involvement in the RM Roadmap project process so far, have you noticed an increase in engagement within your national RM community?

Yes, certainly, the RM Roadmap project has raised awareness of the European Research Management Initiative and has been of great inspiration for issuing discussions on RM challenges on different forums.

The RM's contributions from Spain are remarkable, representing the largest community in Europe on the KCP discussions with 2497 views, and well represented in the ongoing surveys. I would also highlight the effort of the 4 voluntary representatives working as National ambassadors and 5 Thematic ambassadors from the country. This has allowed for broad discussions among us, ensuring awareness of the co-creation process of the RM Roadmap project to the Spanish community and having a good representation in the related European forums.

This initiative has opened broader strategic debates on how to support RM professionalisation and recognise their work, both at the National and regional levels. Take as an example, the before-mentioned joint position to approach the Spanish R&I Ministry or the Research Managers event in Catalonia with more than 350 attendees. The event compelled good practices exchanges on professional development, emotional well-being, or the value of research management, among others, and pointed out the participative opportunities and results from the European projects, RM Roadmap and CARDEA on the research management competencies and career framework proposals.

RM Roadmap ambassadors of Norway:

As the Norwegian ambassador Team to the RM Roadmap project, we are honoured to contribute to this transformative important initiative for RMAs across Europe. The project has impacted multiple levels, enhancing our understanding of the research management profession and fostering community building across Europe. The project management by EARMA, with dedicated personnel supporting ambassadors, has been exemplary. We are confident that this project will have great impact both in the short and long term. Thank you for allowing us to be part of this excellent initiative!

RM Roadmap ambassador of Slovenia:

When we were given an opportunity to enter the RM Roadmap project via the ambassador window, we were excited and of course, seized an opportunity to boost Slovenian RMA activities.

Despite no formal association, the RMA community in Slovenia is present and functioning on an informal level, where active members know each other well, some even for several years. The mentioned network is open for new members, we even try to encourage newcomers to join regardless of their level of expertise. We use reliable communication channels (mailing lists, personal connections, RMA events...).

With the RM Roadmap project, we try to involve as many RMAs as possible, share country-specific outputs with the Slovenian RMA society and of course represent best practices from other EU countries.

When the first RM Roadmap co-creation session was released, we figured out that the RM community is quite big, currently consisting of 95 members. In spite of that, we still think that there are plenty of other (currently not involved) Slovenian RMAs that could join this initiative and enrich our group. But on the other hand, we face another challenge – only a smaller part of our community is active and manages to contribute to the ongoing debate. We are convinced that the contribution rate would be much greater if a formal association would exist. Later in my personal opinion with the following explanation: formal association is in my view a higher level of a certain community compared to an informal one - that is because once RMA members manage to construct such a formal

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society, they already have some more definite goals and are willing to accept a burden of formal association as they know this can bring additional benefits.

We feel that with the introduction of the RM Roadmap project to our community, we managed to raise awareness in our RMA network. We are receiving inquiries regarding future actions and events. This encourages us to think about our next step – grounding Slovenian ARMA.

More testimonials available [here](#).

RM ROADMAP

 rmroadmap.eu

 [@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

 [linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap)

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